

The Upper Palaeolithic occupation and stratigraphy at Trenčianske Bohuslavice, Western Carpathians, Slovakia

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Abstract

Trenčianske Bohuslavice Gravettian site has been known since the early 1980s with possibly having the longest Upper Palaeolithic sequence in the region including a peculiar assemblage of lithic tools composed of bifacial leaf points. This paper presents the results of the 2017 excavation season that produced new data on the absolute chronology, stratigraphy, palaeobotany, archaeology, archaeozoology of the site. We found that the earliest occupation most probably belongs to the Aurignacian. This is followed by two Late Gravettian layers and the layer that yielded the bifacial leaf points. An Early Epigravettian layer seals the sequence dated to 26 ky cal BP. The succession of biological remains and geological evidences enabled to reconstruct a cooling climate and disappearing boreal forest, which corresponded well with the development of the last glacial maximum.

Keywords

Late Gravettian, Epigravettian, Last Glacial Maximum, lithic armature, bifacial leaf point

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1 **1. Introduction**

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3 Complete Upper Palaeolithic (UP) archaeological sequences are rare for the
4 Weichselian glacial period in eastern Central Europe (ECE). The longest sequence of UP human
5 occupations is from Willendorf II, Lower Austria, which consists of Early Aurignacian, Early
6 Gravettian, Pavlovian, and Late Gravettian occupations between 43.5 and 27 ky cal BP (Otte
7 1981; Haesaerts et al. 1996; Moreau 2009; Nigst 2012; Nigst et al. 2014). In southern Moravia,
8 the Dolní Věstonice brickyard also provides a long Weichselian stratigraphic sequence, but the
9 succession of human occupations near Pavlov Hills is fewer than at Willendorf II, consisting of
10 several Pavlovian sites that are sometimes underlain by uncharacteristic UP lithic assemblages
11 contemporaneous with the 34 ky cal BP old Early Gravettian of Willendorf II (Novák 2016;
12 Svoboda 2016). Additionally, Early Upper Palaeolithic (EUP) Aurignacian layers are missing
13 around the Pavlov Hills, and the human occupations halted before the Late Upper Palaeolithic
14 (LUP) Epigravettian of the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) (Klíma 1963, 1990; Svoboda 1997,
15 2005, 2007, 2016; Oliva 2009, 2016). Indeed, it is exceptional when a LUP layer seals a UP
16 series of human occupations in ECE, and when it does so, then the EUP layer is missing, such
17 as the case with the Gravettian–Epigravettian succession at Pilisszántó I rockshelter in Hungary
18 (Dobosi and Vörös 1987; Lengyel 2016) or at Kašov I in eastern Slovakia (Novák 2004;
19 Kaminská 2014). According to the available archaeological record, the only site in ECE which
20 may have contained occupations from each UP subperiod was found at the village Trenčianske
21 Bohuslavice (hereafter abbreviated as TrB) in western Slovakia (Bárta 1988). Although
22 excavations were carried out at the site between 1981 and 1986, the archaeological sequence of
23 TrB has remained unclear due to the lack of published details, even though the archaeological
24 record of the site had promise of a long UP sequence in ECE. In this paper, we present new data
25 that clarify the number of human occupations and the relevant archaeological cultures recovered
26 at TrB, which contribute to our knowledge about the Upper Pleniglacial human occupations of
27 eastern Central Europe.

28 29 **2. Trenčianske Bohuslavice site**

30 31 **2.1. Location**

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33 Trenčianske Bohuslavice is a village situated in western Slovakia, in the Slovak-
34 Moravian Carpathians, a part of the Outer Western Carpathians (Fig. 1). It is 14 km southwest
35 of Trenčín, in the valley of Bošáčka Stream which is a right tributary of the Váh, which is the
36 main river of this region. The opening of Bošáčka valley from the Váh is narrow. The
37 archaeological area is located outside of the centre of the village and is called Pod Tureckom.
38 Pod Tureckom was the local brickyard of the village until the late 1970s. Earthmoving at the
39 brickyard uncovered mammoth remains in the early 20th century and artefacts have been found
40 since World War II (Bárta 1967, 1988). The archaeological site is found on the northern lower
41 slopes of Turecký Vrch (Turkish Hill) (346 meters above sea level, hereafter m a.s.l.),
42 immediately behind the narrow pass of Bošáčka. The elevation of the site is 204–206 m a.s.l.,
43 10–15 m above the bottom of the Bošáčka Stream bed.

44
45 *Figure 1. Location of Trenčianske Bohuslavice.*

46 47 **2.2. Previous research**

50 The first set of excavations at the site were carried out between 1981 and 1986 (Bárta
51 1988). J. Bárta opened three areas to excavate, A, B, and C (Fig. 2). Area A contained two sets
52 of trenches placed 25 m apart from each other. In the first location of this area (A1), a large part
53 of the sediment covering the archaeological layer was removed by bulldozer. About 75 meters
54 from area A westwards, a 7 m deep section was exposed in a deep gully running west–east,
55 exposing the stratigraphy of the Pod Tureckom area. Area B was opened up from the
56 stratigraphic section of the gully wall, oriented to the north. In 1983 a second set of trenches
57 was excavated in A (area A2) west to the bulldozered area A1 (Bárta 1986). The third location,
58 area C, was tested about 50 meters north of area A, but after yielding a few archaeological finds
59 the excavation was not continued. Altogether, Bárta (1981, 1982, 1983, 1984, 1985, 1986,
60 1988) found four archaeological levels in the site’s different excavation areas.

61
62 *Figure 2. Excavation trenches at Trenčianske Bohuslavice.*

63
64 The uppermost archaeological level, 70–80 cm under the surface in area A2, was
65 classified as Gravettian. Animal bones such as from reindeer and horse marked this layer in the
66 stratum, and lithic artefacts were fewer than in other layers, but this layer contained a stone-
67 paved hearth (Bárta 1988, fig). Bárta marked this stratigraphic unit layer III. The “main
68 Gravettian” occupation (layer II) lay beneath layer III. According to Bárta (1988), these two
69 layers were embedded within a calcareous loess formed during the Würm 3 stadial. Layer II
70 yielded an abundant collection of knapped lithic artefacts. The third and lowermost
71 archaeological layer (layer I) was below layer II in area A1. This layer was associated with the
72 Würm 2–3 interstadial soil. Compared to layer II, layer I yielded fewer lithic artefacts and
73 animal bones were almost absent.

74 In area B, the human occupation was found 260–290 cm under the surface in a single
75 layer. Area B was excavated through two trenches: 1B/82 in 1982 and 2B/83 in 1983. The
76 findings included lithic artefacts, animal bones, pierced quartzite pebbles, and hearths. The
77 hearths in area B had been disturbed by solifluction. The Area B lithic tools compositions
78 differed from the compositions of area A1 and A2 by containing bifacial leaf points (BLPs).
79 However, no correlation was made between the layers of areas A1–A2 and B.

80 In 2008, Vlačiky et al. (2013) reopened 2 m² in area A2 to collect samples for stable
81 isotope analysis (⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr, ¹³C/¹²C and ¹⁵N/¹⁴N) of the paleontological remains, and also to
82 collect samples for radiocarbon dating and for sedimentological, malacozoological,
83 palynological, and lithic studies. Vlačiky et al. (2013) found three archaeological layers in area
84 A2. The uppermost layer was between 25 and 35 cm below the recent surface, the second
85 between 55 and 75 cm, and the third between 85 and 125 cm. The uppermost layer cannot be
86 correlated with any layers in Bárta’s stratigraphy. The second layer was equal to layer III of
87 Bárta due to the similar depth in area A2 and the presence of animal bones and the scarcity of
88 lithics. The lowermost layer can be identified as layer II of Bárta, which yielded the greatest
89 number of lithic artefacts.

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91 **2.3. Radiocarbon dating results from the previous research**

92

93 Radiocarbon dates were obtained from both former excavations (Table 1). Bárta (1988)
94 published a date 22,000 ± 600 rcBP (Ge-4009) from the archaeological layer of area B, which
95 was obtained from charcoals of the distorted hearths. The laboratory code “Ge” was given in
96 error for Gliwice laboratory in Poland, correctly identified by Gd. A slightly different date with
97 the same laboratory number is also given in the same paper, 22,500 ± 600 rcBP, but this time
98 with the correct laboratory code (Gd-4009). Bárta assigned this date to a stone structured hearth
99 in area A2 trench 29/85, found in layer III of Bárta’s division. However, the date Gd-4009 was

100 obtained from a sample taken off the combustion features of area B according to the original
101 submission sheets stored in the archives of the Gliwice Radiocarbon Laboratory, Poland. A few
102 pages later in the same publication (Bárta 1988, p. 181) the date Gd-4009 was correctly assigned
103 to the BLP assemblage in area B. The next date mentioned by Bárta (1988) is $20,300 \pm 500$
104 rcBP (Gd-4011) obtained from trench 26–27/84–85 (area A2) on charcoals of a hearth situated
105 70 cm under the surface of layer III of Bárta. The charcoals of this hearth were identified as
106 *Picea abies* and other *Pinopsida* species (Bárta 1988). Layer II of Bárta was dated to $23,000 \pm$
107 1300 rcBP (Gd-4010) in trench 23/83 of area A2 on charcoals from a hearth. The charcoals also
108 were of *Picea abies* and other *Pinopsida* species. No dates were eventually obtained for the
109 lowest layer (layer I) embedded in the interstadial soil.

110 Verpoorte (2002) also obtained dates on charcoals collected by Bárta in the 1980s. A
111 total of five dates were published (Table 1) along with a hitherto unmentioned date without
112 trench number and depth data: $23,700 \pm 500$ rcBP (Gd-2490). According to the Gliwice
113 Radiocarbon Laboratory Archives, the sample of this date derived from trench 28/85 in area
114 A2, 1.80 m below the surface. One of the dates was significantly older than the others: $29,910$
115 ± 260 rcBP (GrA-16139). This date was assigned to trench “IB/18” and obtained from a sample
116 taken at 1.20 m under the recent surface. Such a trench number, however, did not exist and there
117 was no archaeological layer mentioned from this elevation in area B. This date, however, could
118 be associated with area 1B and digits “18” marking the year could have been inadvertently
119 transposed instead of ’81, the year when the stratigraphic section in the gully wall was made in
120 1981.

121 Vlačíky et al. (2013) published the third set of dates from area A2. The uppermost layer
122 was dated to $22,330 \pm 110$ rcBP (GrA-42311), the second layer that equals layer III of Bárta
123 was dated to $23,210 \pm 130$ rcBP (GrA-44244), and the lowermost layer that corresponds to layer
124 II of Bárta was dated to $24,540 \pm 130$ rcBP (GrA-42312). Vlačíky et al. (2013) published two
125 further dates yet unmentioned making a reference to Zaár’s (2007) unpublished dissertation,
126 which were obtained from area B at 1.80 m depth ($22,800 \pm 600$ rcBP; Gd-4016) and from area
127 A2 trench 29/85 0.90 m depth ($23,400 \pm 700$ rcBP; Gd-4014).

128
129 *Table 1. Radiocarbon dates of the site*

130 131 **3. Materials and methods**

132 133 **3.1. Field methods**

134
135 Two areas of the site were excavated in 2017: A2 and B. In area A2, we opened a trench
136 of 10 m^2 in the unexcavated corner of Bárta’s trenches of 1983 (Fig. 2). In area B, 18 m^2 were
137 exposed on the western edge of Bárta’s trench 1B/82 (Fig. 2). Recovery methods included hand-
138 collection and wet-sieving using mesh size 1 mm. The positions of archaeological finds and
139 animal remains were recorded by total station.

140 141 **3.2. Geology**

142
143 Descriptions of archaeological exposures were made on the basis of geological and
144 paleopedological criteria. The subjects of the analysis were sediment-soil sequences available
145 for direct studies in key sections. Their basic units were geological layers (loess) separated by
146 soil and/or archaeological horizons. In addition, drilling has been carried out in each section to
147 reach primary loess. For each part of the archaeological trenches, descriptions of key sequences
148 were constructed. The following criteria were taken into account: lithology, structure, colour,
149 carbonate content, and the presence of Mn and Fe concentrations. In addition, three sections

150 were sampled for particle size analysis at intervals of 10 cm (recent soil) and 5 cm (loess and
151 archaeological layers). The grain size measurements were made based on the laser diffraction
152 method (instrument Malvern Mastersizer 2000) according to the methodology proposed by
153 Újvári et al. (2016).

154 155 **3.3. Dating**

156
157 Samples for radiocarbon dating were taken from each archaeological layer. Bones and
158 charcoals were selected for dating. Charcoals were both hand-collected and floated from
159 archaeological sediments through 0.5 and 1.0 mm mesh.

160 Wood charcoals were identified taxonomically prior to radiocarbon dating. When
161 possible, branch wood or twigs were selected since this kind of wood might be an optimal
162 material to avoid the old wood effect (Moskal-del Hoyo and Kozłowski 2009; Nowak et al.
163 2017).

164 The AMS radiocarbon dating was performed at Poznan Radiocarbon Laboratory.
165 Methods of chemical pre-treatment at Poznan Laboratory are available online (Goslar n.d.),
166 according to which the lab follows the protocol of the Oxford Radiocarbon Accelerator Unit
167 (Brock et al. 2010). Extraction of bone collagen was performed according to Piotrowska and
168 Goslar (2002). Bone samples were regarded suitable for collagen dating if nitrogen content was
169 not lower than 0.6%, and C/N ratio was within the interval of 2.7–3.5. The AMS dating
170 procedure followed Czernik and Goslar (2001). Content of ^{14}C was measured using a 0.5 MV
171 NEC machine (Goslar et al. 2004). Radiocarbon dates were calibrated with OxCal (Reimer et
172 al. 2013) indicating 95.4% probability.

173 174 **3.4. Paleobotany**

175
176 The present study is based on two kinds of samples: 1) floated samples of a total volume
177 of 126 litres of sediment using meshes of 0.5 and 1.0 mm; and 2) manually collected samples.
178 Charred wood anatomy was studied applying a reflected light microscope with magnifications
179 of 100, 200, and 500 to observe three anatomical sections of the wood: transverse section,
180 longitudinal radial section, and longitudinal tangential section in freshly broken charcoal
181 fragments. Taxonomical identifications were made by comparing the specimens with the
182 modern wood collections of the Department of Palaeobotany of the W. Szafer Institute of
183 Botany PAS and atlases of wood anatomy (Greguss 1955; Schweingruber 1990). The charcoal
184 of *Pinus* type *sylvestris-mugo* was identified based on the presence of large fenestriform pits
185 and ray tracheids with dentated walls in cross-fields, while the identification of *Pinus cembra*
186 was based on the presence of large fenestriform pits and ray tracheids with smooth walls in
187 cross-fields. Badly preserved charcoals with large fenestriform pits were recognized as *Pinus*
188 sp. Based on wood anatomy it is not possible to distinguish between two genera: *Picea* and
189 *Larix*, thus both genera are identified to one taxon. Coniferous wood without specifying the
190 species was indicated when details of cross-fields could not have been observed due to poor
191 state of preservation.

192 Additional dendrological analysis focused on ring curvature observations were
193 performed (Marguerie and Hunot 2007) and the presence of decayed wood was noted (Moskal-
194 del Hoyo et al. 2010). Charcoals were also investigated using a scanning electron microscope
195 (SEM Hitachi S-4700) at the Laboratory of Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy and
196 Microanalysis at the Institute of Geological Sciences of the Jagiellonian University (Kraków,
197 Poland).

198 199 **3.5. Archaeozoology**

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The bone remains were identified applying a comparative collection of the Institute of Systematics and Evolution of Animals (Polish Academy of Sciences, Kraków) and published data (Gramova 1950; Pales and Garcia 1981a, 1981b). Two quantified calculations were made: NISP (Number of Identified Specimens) and MNI (Minimal Number of Individuals) (Klein and Cruz-Urbe 1984; Lyman 1994). All bone remains were subjected to detailed observations in order to identify impacts of humans, carnivores, rodents, and plant root activity (Sutcliffe 1970; Haynes 1980, 1983; Binford 1981; Shipman and Rose 1983; Shipman et al., 1984; Olsen and Shipman 1988; Lyman 1994; Stiner et al. 1995; Bennet 1999; Théry-Parisot 2002; Villa et al. 2002). Each mark was examined under low-power magnification.

3.6. Malacology

Snail shells were identified to species level whenever possible. Nomenclature followed Welter-Schultes (2012). *Pupilla pratensis* (Clessin 1871) was not distinguished from *Pupilla muscorum* (Linnaeus 1758) until recently (von Proschwitz et al. 2009). Due to their close conchological similarity, we treated all *P. muscorum*-like shells as *P. muscorum*. Ecological information on each species followed Ložek (1964), Kerney et al. (1983), Meng and Hoffmann (2009), Welter-Schultes (2012) and Horsák et al. (2013).

3.7. Lithic tools

We studied 686 lithic tools discovered in areas A2 and B in the 1980s and 2017. The materials from area A1 were excluded because the bulldozer work truncated the sequence and the lithics cannot be securely paired with archaeological layers.

Lithic raw materials were identified macroscopically following Přichystal (2013) and the Lithoteca collection of the Hungarian National Museum (Biró and Dobosi 1991; Biró et al. 2000) and the Lithic Reference Collection of the ELTE University of Budapest (Mester 2013).

A lithic tool here is defined as a knapped stone product whose edges were modified by retouching or burin spall removals. The tools were analysed in terms of lithic raw material, blanks of the tools, typology, and use-wear. We differentiated raw materials by their type which also provides information about their geographic origin.

The blanks of the tools were classified as either blade, flake, or debris. The category blade includes the small specimens (bladelets).

The tools were divided into major type classes: end-scrapers, burins, edge retouched tools, perforators, truncations, splintered tools, combined tools, knives, and armatures. We included notched and denticulated artefacts within the group of edge retouched tools. The category of armatures was subdivided into points, backed, and backed-truncated artefacts. The points were further divided into Gravette/microgravette point, fléchette, Vachons point, retouched point, and BLPs categories. BLPs included unfinished bifacial tools as well. The Gravette/microgravette definition here was restricted to those specimens having inverse flat basal or rarely distal retouch opposed to the backed edge (Lengyel 2016, 2018).

The use-wear analysis aimed at determining the function of the lithic tool. The microscopic analysis was carried out at the Laboratory of Archaeometry and Archaeological Conservation, Institute of Archaeology, University of Wrocław. Experiments involving bifacial hafted points in hunting and butchering (Kufel-Diakowska and Bronowicki 2017) were used as a reference. Scars were analysed with the use of Olympus SZX9 stereomicroscope (up to ×114 magnification). Polish, edge rounding, and striations were identified under Nikon ECLIPSE LV100 metallographic microscope (×50–500 magnification). Prior to microscopic observations, the artefacts were cleaned in an ultrasonic tank.

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4. Results

4.1. Geology and stratigraphy

In area A2, aeolian sediments lay directly under the thin top ploughed soil horizon. The archaeological layers were embedded in loess and loess-like sediments, which according to the grain size analyses are typical aeolian periglacial formations. The content of the loess fraction (20-50 µm) is variable and falls within the range of 25-40%. The diversity of these sediments underlines the distinct variability of average grain size (Md) which suggests these are stratified sediments composed mainly of silt and sand and interpreted as redeposited aeolian-slope loess-like sediments.

The uppermost archaeological layer (A2-1) was situated near the top of the calcaric loess (Fig. 3), marked by charcoals and Mn-Fe and Fe oxide concretions, knapped lithics, and a hearth. The thickness of the layer was ~5 cm. This layer was correlated with Layer 1 of Vlačiky et al. (2013).

Figure 3. The eastern wall of A2 trench in 2017; marked are the positions of the archaeological layers. Black dots mark lithic finds, grey dots mark bones in the stratigraphy. Grey lines with grey dots mark bones of multiple measurements.

The second archaeological layer in area A2 (A2-2) lay 30 cm beneath layer A2-1 still in calcaric loess. This layer was correlated with Bárta's uppermost archaeological layer (layer III) and Layer 2 of the excavation in 2008; similarly, the findings were mostly animal bones and a few knapped lithics. Charcoals were sporadic and the small concretions of iron oxide found in layer A2-1 were missing. This archaeological layer cannot be distinguished by geological data.

The third archaeological layer of area A2 (layer A2-3) was situated 40 cm beneath A2-2 in loess. Compared to A2-1, A2-3 was extremely abundant in charcoals, iron oxide concretions, hard-burnt loess fragments, animal bones, and knapped lithics. This layer can be correlated with the 'main Gravettian occupation' of Bárta's excavation (layer II) and Layer 3 of 2008.

We did not find the lowermost layer (layer I) of Bárta.

Figure 4. The correlation of the archaeological layers in areas A2, B1 and B2.

In area B, two trenches were opened, B1 and B2, separated by a 1 m thick unexcavated area. B1 was situated south of B2. In both trenches, the stratigraphy started with a well-developed zonal Luvisol type soil of Late Glacial-Holocene origin ca. 1.60 m thick which preserved only the B and lower horizons due to being truncated on the top (Fig. 4). The border between the Luvisol and the underlying loess was very pronounced in the content of carbonates. The upper archaeological layer was found only in B2 (layer B-1) and correlated with the only archaeological layer of Bárta in area B, which lay 2.60–2.90 m beneath the surface (Fig. 5). Layer B-1 was embedded in loess and marked by irregular charcoal bands, patches of burnt loess surfaces, scattered charcoal and iron oxide concretions, animal bones, and knapped lithics. The morphology of the archaeological layer basically indicates its development in the form of poorly developed soil with traces of local redeposition and allows the traces to be recognized as typical weakly developed soil units formed as gley crysols in a periglacial environment. This layer is decalcified or weakly calcified. Its main features are root pseudomorphs, coprolites, and artefacts. Its colour was sharply darker than the embedding sedimentary environment showing the characteristics of gley (redoximorphic) processes. The activity of soil

300 processes and slope deformations in this layer are confirmed by the analysis of grain size. The
301 average grain size is clearly drifting within the archaeological layer, or it increases by leaps and
302 bounds towards the uppermost horizon (Fig. 6). The activity of aeolian processes is reflected
303 by the peaks of increased sand accumulation.

304

305 *Figure 5. The position of the archaeological layer B-2 in trench B2 in 2017.*

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307 The lower layer of area B, layer B-2, was found in trench B1 (Fig. 4), 1 m south of the
308 excavation limit of B2, about 1.50 m beneath layer B-1. Layer B-2 was a weakly developed soil
309 marked with a few archaeological remains including charcoals and knapped lithics. This layer
310 was not mentioned in reports from work in the 1980s. Based on the similar geological positions,
311 this tentatively could be correlated with the lowermost archaeological layer of the 1980s (layer
312 I) situated in area A1 under the ‘main Gravettian occupation’ (layer II) in an interstadial soil.

313

314 *Table 2. Litho- and pedological characteristic of trenches A2, B1 and B2.*

315

316 *Figure 6. Results of the sedimentological analyses in trenches B2 and A2.*

317

318 The correlation of the stratigraphic sequences between area A2 and area B is not
319 straightforward because the top of the section in area A2 was truncated down to the aeolian
320 sediment. A fixed stratigraphic marker can be the interstadial soil under A2-3, which
321 corresponds with the soil in B that contained the lower archaeological layer (B-2). According
322 to this position, A2-3 is younger than B-2. Further correlations can be achieved relying on other
323 data.

324

325 **4.2. Chronology**

326

327 Nine new dating samples were obtained from the 2017 excavation (Table 1). Layer A2-
328 1 was dated to $22,370 \pm 150$ rcBP (Poz-97252) on a charcoal of *Pinus sylvestris-mugo* taken
329 from a hearth.

330 Layer A2-2 was dated $23,850 \pm 230$ rcBP (Poz-101182) derived from a *Mammuthus*
331 *primigenius* rib fragment, and $25,130 \pm 270$ rcBP (Poz-101178) derived from a piece of
332 mammoth vertebra.

333 Layer A2-3 dates were also made on bones: $25,560 \pm 290$ rcBP (Poz-101180) was
334 measured on a *Rangifer* metacarpal bone, and a date $25,910 \pm 300$ rcBP (Poz-101181) was from
335 a *Rangifer* radius bone.

336 Concerning Layer B-1, all bone samples failed to yield a sufficient amount of collagen.
337 However, charcoal samples taken from three charcoal bands (Fig. 7) separated by a few
338 centimetres of loess yielded three dates. The charcoals were of *Pinus* sp., *Picea* sp./*Larix* sp.,
339 and a coniferous tree. From within the second band (middle), remains of twigs were dated. The
340 stratigraphic order of the dates is reversed. The lowest date, $22,180 \pm 220$ rcBP (Poz-97362), is
341 significantly younger than the two others above this: $24,560 \pm 180$ rcBP (Poz-97254) and
342 $24,600 \pm 180$ rcBP (Poz-97253). Layer B-2 was dated on charcoal to $32,790 \pm 460$ rcBP (Poz-
343 101822).

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345 *Figure 7. The three charcoal bands in trench B2 western wall. Indicated are the origins of the*
346 *radiocarbon samples.*

347

348 All radiocarbon dates obtained from the two areas of the site are divided among five
349 layers. The first three are located in area A2, and they have a direct superposition. The fourth

350 and the fifth layers are in area B. Plotting the dates with 95.4% probability after calibration with
351 OxCal (Reimer et al. 2013) in BP years shows a tendency for aging towards lower stratigraphic
352 positions in area A2. The age $22,370 \pm 150$ rcBP (Poz-97252) of layer A2-1 is identical to $22,330$
353 ± 110 rcBP (GrA-42311) obtained by Vlačičky et al. (2013) for the same layer. Below in layer
354 A2-2, however, there is one outlier date $20,300 \pm 500$ rcBP (Gd-4011). In layer A2-3 there is
355 one insecure date, Gd-4010, that has a large standard deviation, 1300 radiocarbon years.
356 Removing these dates from the list we see that the most possible age of the uppermost
357 occupation (layer A2-1) after calibration is 26-27 ky cal BP. Layer A2-2 is 27-28 ky cal BP old
358 and layer A2-3 dates to 28-30 ky cal BP.

359 In area B, two of the new dates are significantly older than the rest of the dates. If we
360 regard these two outliers, the age of the B-1 human occupation most likely is 26-27 ky cal BP.
361 However, the reverse order of dates from the microstratigraphy of the 2017 excavation calls for
362 caution estimating the age of this occupation. Layer B-1 in this regard seems to be identical
363 with A2-1 and therefore likely postdates layers A2-2 and A2-3.

364

365 4.3. Charcoals analysis

366

367 Layer A2-1 contained a very small number of charcoal fragments associated with a
368 hearth. Only remains of *Pinus t. sylvestris-mugo* were identified (n=8). In layer A2-2 *Picea* sp.
369 or *Larix* sp. were found (n=13) dispersed within the layer. Layer A2-3 yielded *Pinus cembra*
370 (n=41), *Pinus* sp. (n=39), *Picea* sp. or *Larix* sp. (n=141), and coniferous wood (n=47). The most
371 abundant samples came from a hearth of layer A2-3 (n=207) and in this context the remains of
372 *Picea* sp. or *Larix* sp. were dominant (n=117). With the exception of hearth remains, all other
373 charcoal assemblages contained very small charcoal fragments that usually did not exceed 2-3
374 mm in transverse section. Charcoals of layer A2-3 were infected by fungi and xylophagous
375 insects. Part of them had originated from branchwood as they were characterized by a presence
376 of compression wood; as well, some twigs were documented. The majority of *Picea* sp. or *Larix*
377 sp. fragments had narrow rings. Fragments of bark were also found.

378 The Layer B-1 charcoal assemblage included *Pinus cembra* (n=21), *Pinus* sp. (n=27),
379 *Picea* sp. or *Larix* sp. (n=98), and coniferous wood (n=34). These samples were also frequently
380 infected by fungi. Layer B-2 yielded only *Picea* sp. or *Larix* sp. (n=5). They were characterized
381 by the presence of fungi.

382

383 4.4. Animal remains

384

385 Animal remains were discovered in layers A2-2, A2-3 and B-1. The bones are heavily
386 fragmented, which makes identification of element and taxon very difficult or impossible. The
387 fragmentation was due to both post-depositional processes and human activity that split long
388 bones into small fragments to use as hearth fuel, especially in layer A2-3. Bones were relatively
389 often covered by root etching. Layer A2-1 and B-2 did not contain animal remains other than
390 mollusc shells. In layer A2-2 single bones were found of mammoth (mainly vertebrae), wolf,
391 and arctic/red fox. Layer A2-3 contained the most abundant animal remains, including
392 mammoth (NISP=29, MNI=1), reindeer (NISP=41, MNI=2), wolf (NISP=21, MNI=1),
393 Arctic/red fox (NISP=2, MNI=1), and hare (NISP=7, MNI=1). Additionally, in this layer single
394 bones of unidentified bird and rodents were also noted. Layer B1 is similar to layer A2-2 and
395 A 2-3 in containing remains of mammoth (NISP=25, MNI=2), reindeer (NISP=7, MNI=1), wolf
396 (NISP=13, MNI=1), and Arctic/red fox (NISP=12, MNI=1). In layer A2-3 and B-1 some
397 skeletal elements of carnivores were preserved in anatomical order. Generally, material
398 identified to species/genus have been known from earlier studies of this site (Vlačičky et al.,
399 2013). A new discovery is of rodents (*Microtus agrestis*, *Microtus gregalis*, and *Microtus*

400 *oeconomus*) from layer A2-2. Direct traces of human activity such as cut- or punch marks are
401 few, which can be explained by the poor state of bone preservation. However, the context of
402 their discovery (a human settlement discovered together with numerous artefacts and artificial
403 structures) indicates that animal remains at the site are results of human activity.

404

405 **4.5. Knapped lithics**

406

407 The distribution of the raw materials used in the formal tool kits was different between
408 the archaeological layers. What is especially important is that the proportions of the lithic raw
409 materials in the tool assemblages accurately represent the complete collections.

410 Identified were five types of lithic raw materials in the formal toolkits of the layers. First
411 is the erratic flint originating closest from glacial deposits of the Moravian gate (Přichystal
412 2013). This flint is of Cretaceous origin. Another type of flint is of Jurassic origin, which is
413 found at the Kraków-Częstochowa Upland in Poland (Kaczanowska and Kozłowski 1976), but
414 a coarser variant of this flint can be found at Stránská Skála outcrop of Southern Moravia
415 (Přichystal 2013). Polish Jurassic flint in most cases has a brownish hue and finer texture. The
416 Moravian type is predominantly of greyish hue. Locally available raw material at TrB was the
417 radiolarite originating in the Klippen Belt of the White Carpathians (Přichystal 2013). The
418 obsidian in the assemblages derived from Tokaj Mountains of northeastern Hungary, type
419 Carpathian 2 (Kasztovszky and Přichystal 2018). The fifth raw material category includes
420 various siliceous rocks called limnic silicite. These were formed by post volcanic activity of
421 Miocene age in lacustrine sedimentary environment (Přichystal 2013). Closest sources are in
422 Central Slovakia but they might have originated from the volcanic ranges in north Hungary, as
423 well.

424

425 *Table 3. Trenčianske Bohuslavice lithic tool kit raw material composition.*

426

427 Layer A2-1 tool assemblage is made of radiolarite (n=8), while formal tool assemblages
428 from layers A2-2 (n=122) and A2-3 (n=848) have very similar proportions of raw materials,
429 consisting of radiolarite, erratic flint, Jurassic flint, obsidian, and unidentified chert (Fig. 8). In
430 both assemblages the erratic flint is dominant (54.9 % and 54.5 %); radiolarite is the next most
431 abundant (35.2 % and 35.7 %), while all the other materials make up less than 5.5 %. The sole
432 but slight difference between them is the greater percent of Jurassic flint in A2-3 (5.5 % versus
433 1.6 %). Layer A2-1 tool assemblage is made of radiolarite (n=8). In layer B-1 radiolarite
434 dominates (88.5 %), supplemented by erratic flint (10.3%) and chert (1.1 %). Only one
435 specimen of radiolarite retouched tool was found in layer B-2.

436

437 *Table 4. Trenčianske Bohuslavice retouched tools inventories of areas A2, B1 and B2.*

438

439 Layer A2-1 has no lithic armature and is dominated by domestic tools such as the edge
440 retouched tools, end-scrapers, and burins (Table 4). Tools made on blades make up 62.5 % of
441 the assemblage, and tools made from flakes are in the minority. All edge retouched tools are
442 blades except the splintered tool made from a flake; the other types were made of both blades
443 and flakes.

444 Layers A2-2 yielded a wider spectrum of tool types including the armatures. The
445 assemblage consists of mostly blade tools (84.4 %). Edge retouched tools, burins, and
446 endscrapers dominate the domestic tool assemblage. The largest number of flake tools are
447 burins (n=10) and there are few endscrapers (n=3) and edge retouched tools (n=5); a single
448 borer is made from a flake. The armatures make up 23 % of the tool assemblage. Within
449 armatures backed bladelets and retouched blade points are the most numerous.

450 The Layer A2-3 tool assemblage is also strongly dominated by blade tools (92.1 %).
451 Flake tools are most often burins (n=27), splintered tools (n=18), edge retouched tools (n=10),
452 or endscrapers (n=5). The domestic tool spectrum is almost identical to what is found in the
453 Layer A2-2 assemblage. The armatures make up 20.5 %, within which the
454 Gravette/microgravette group, absent in Layer A2-2, presents several items (Fig. 8).

455 The Layer B-1 tool kit is also dominated by blades (63.2 %) and most of the flakes are
456 edge-retouched tools (n=9). The blanks of the BLPs are classified as unknown because the
457 retouching removed all diagnostic features needed to identify blank types. There are two BLPs
458 on which unretouched removal scar surfaces were preserved, thus we suppose the blanks of the
459 unknown BLPs were also flakes. Armatures make up 25.3 % of the assemblage with the
460 dominance of BLPs. The single tool of layer B-2 is a retouched flake.

461
462 *Figure 8. Formal tools of layer A2-3 (1-15) and layer B-1 (16-21). 1–3: end-scraper; 4–5:*
463 *burin; 6: retouched blade; 7: splintered tool; 8–10: microgravette; 11: Vachons point; 12–*
464 *13: backed and ventrally truncated bladelets (Late Gravettian rectangle) 14: fléchette; 15:*
465 *retouched point; 16, 17, 19, 20: bifacial leaf point; 19: bifacial knife. 1, 5–9, 12, 14: erratic*
466 *flint; 2, 4, 6: Jurassic flint; 3, 10: obsidian Carpathian 2 type; 11, 15–20: radiolarite; 13:*
467 *chert.*

468

469 **4.6. Use-wear analysis**

470

471 Use-wear analysis of BLP specimens (Fig. 8: 16-18) from the 2017 excavation showed
472 two different methods of utilization. The tip of the yellow-brown radiolarite tool (Fig. 8: 17)
473 was crushed with bifacial step and hinged bending fractures (Fig. 9: 1A). Fragments of the
474 lateral edges near the tip are rounded and slightly polished. The polished area is cut through by
475 short and narrow striations, parallel to the cutting edge (Fig. 9: 1B). Bright haft polish is visible
476 in the middle part of one of the surfaces, mostly on the dorsal ridges (Fig. 9: 1C-D). These
477 traces indicate that this BLP was inserted into the tip of a spear and used for hunting. Another
478 BLP specimen of brown radiolarite (Fig. 8: 18) was unfinished probably due to breakage during
479 production. After this accident the right lateral edge remained roughed-out but retouched, and
480 the left edge was shaped to have a sharp tip. There are no fractures on this tip, but the left edge
481 adjoining the tip is rounded and covered by greasy polish, with visible tiny scratches parallel to
482 the cutting edge (Fig. 9: 2A-B). This tool was used as a handheld knife for cutting soft animal
483 tissue. The third specimen made of brown radiolarite showed no sign of use (Fig. 8: 16). We
484 also analysed 14 bifacial thinning flakes made from brown (n=8) and green (n=5) radiolarite
485 and flint (n=1). These pieces had no use-wear, therefore we did not find proof for re-sharpening
486 bifacial tools at the site.

487

488 *Figure 9. Use wear traces on bifacial tools.*

489

490 **4.7. Adornments**

491

492 Bárta (1988) reported pendants made of flat limestone pebbles without specifying their
493 manufacturing technology and the number of finds. All pebble pendants were found in area B
494 in association with the BLP lithic industry (layer B-1).

495 The collection consists of 14 modified pebbles, of which 13 are drilled and one shows
496 the mark of drilling although a penetrating hole was not achieved (Fig. 10). Except for one, all
497 the drilled specimens were made of white quartzite pebbles. The exception is a greyish-brown
498 sandstone pebble. A total of eight specimens of the drilled pebbles are complete and five are
499 broken. The breakage always occurred at the eye of the pendant. The pendant eye was made in

500 each case by perforating both faces of the pebble. The eyes therefore are biconical in section.
501 The outline of the quartzite pebbles are naturally tear-drop or oval, while the one sandstone
502 item is circular in shape. The original outline of the pebble always remained intact.

503 Two items were further decorated with paired parallel incised lines on edges of the
504 pebbles (Fig. 10: 1A, B; 2A, B). One pendant has five pairs of lines on one edge, and six pairs
505 of lines on the other edge (Fig. 10: 2A). The second incised pebble has three pairs of lines (Fig.
506 10: 2B).

507 By length, the pendants can be divided into two groups: greater than 35 mm, and shorter
508 than 25 mm. By thickness, most items are thinner than 8 mm. By width, most are narrower than
509 25 mm. The sandstone item is always an outlier. The incised items belong to the larger kind of
510 pendant. Most broken items and the unfinished specimen belong to the smaller kind. It is
511 unclear whether the broken items were damaged during production or while in use.

512 Apart from the pierced pendants, blanks for making pendants were also found solely in
513 area B. A total of 42 small flat pebbles were found by Bárta in the 1980s and 41 items in 2017.
514 The majority of these pebbles are quartzite (n=71), two pebbles are fossils, one is granite, and
515 the rest are limestone or sandstone. The origin of the pebbles is yet unclear since Bošáčka gravel
516 is entirely composed of limestone pebbles and the Váh valley gravel contains mostly limestone
517 and sandstone pebbles, rarely radiolarite pebbles and hardly any quartzite.

518 The only personal ornament of layer A2-3 in area A2 is a pierced canine tooth from a
519 red deer (*Cervus elaphus*), recovered in the 1980s but which remained unpublished (Fig. 10:
520 3). The eye of the pendant is broken and was made at the root of the tooth by perforating from
521 opposites faces, similarly to the drilling of the pebble pendants in area B. Therefore, the shape
522 of the hole is also biconical and the pendant's shape resembles again a tear-drop.

523
524 *Figure 10. Pierced pebble pendants of layer B-1 (1), two of which have incision on their*
525 *edges (2), and the tooth pendant of layer A2-3 (3).*
526

527 **4.8. Malacology**

528

529 Of the 7058 shells, 6987 specimens were identified to species level divided among 17
530 species (Ložek 1954; Welter-Schultes 2012). The most dominant species were *Pupilla*
531 *muscorum* (Linnaeus, 1758) (n=4116) and *Succinella oblonga* (Draparnaud, 1801) (n=1732)
532 (Fig. 11); both taxa inhabit relatively dry, open areas, although they have a wide ecological
533 tolerance. Therefore, their role in reconstructing habitat and climate is moderate.

534 The layer B-1 snail faunal assemblage (n=1476) is divided among twelve species and
535 its spectrum of species is most similar to that of layer A2-1 (n=3734) (Fig. 12) with the
536 occurrence of *Pupilla loessica* (Ložek 1954), *Clausilia dubia* (Draparnaud, 1805), *Vallonia*
537 *tenuilabris* (Braun, 1843), *Trochulus hispidus* (Linnaeus, 1758), and *Columella columella* (G.
538 von Martens, 1830) in both layers. These species are absent or relatively rare in other layers.
539 The most conspicuous difference between layer B-1 and A2-1 is the frequency of *Pupilla sterrii*
540 (Forster, 1840) in the former (n=40), and *Columella columella* in the latter one (n=39). Both
541 species prefer cold climate, and therefore the two species have minor importance in terms of
542 differentiating climate reconstructions for the two layers. A single shell of *Orcula dolium*
543 (Draparnaud, 1801), which is primarily a forest species, was found in layer A2-1, too.

544 The layer A2-2 snail faunal collection (n=1587) consist of ten species whose presence
545 indicates the driest climate among all the snail taxa, as indicated by the frequent occurrence of
546 *Pupilla triplicata* (n=80), the absence/low frequency of hygrophilous species (*Clausilia dubia*,
547 *Trochulus hispidus*, *Cochlicopa lubrica* (O. F. Müller, 1774), *Pseudotrichia rubiginosa*
548 (Rossmässler, 1838)), and the relatively low number of species.

549 The layer A2-3 snail faunal assemblage (n=264) is made up of thirteen species which
550 indicate relatively humid environmental conditions, as signalled by the occurrence of
551 hygrophilous species, such as *Clausilia dubia* and *Cochlicopa lubrica*. *Vestia turgida*
552 (Rossmässler, 1836), which typically inhabits wet marshes and stream banks, was found most
553 frequently in layer A2-3, although it was also found in one sample in layer B-1. A single shell
554 of the hygrophilous *Vitrea crystallina* was found in layer A2-3, further emphasizing the wet
555 climate. The absence of *Columella columella* and *Pupilla loessica* and the decreased number
556 of *Vallonia tenuilabris* in layer A2-3 indicates that the layer's sedimentation occurred in a
557 warmer climate than that of layer A2-1 and B-1.

558
559 *Figure 11. The distribution of mollusc fauna in the archaeological layers.*

560 **5. Discussion and conclusion**

561
562 The most awaited question to answer in regard to the archaeological record of TrB
563 human occupations is the stratigraphic correlation between areas A and B. Former attempts
564 (Verpoorte 2002; Vlačíky et al. 2013) unsuccessfully accomplished this task, mainly due to the
565 fact that stratigraphic depth data of the 1980s was insufficient to reconstruct the order of the
566 radiocarbon samples because the steep slope of Pod Tureckom area behind the Turecký Vrch.
567 This situation was responsible for covering the archaeological layers with significantly varying
568 thicknesses of sediments between areas A2 and B. Therefore, the method of Verpoorte (2002)
569 that sorted the radiocarbon dates and the archaeological layers according to depth data resulted
570 in a mixed order of the human occupations. Another issue that caused inaccuracy in the
571 chronology of the site arose from Bárta's layer numbering. Verpoorte (2002) and Vlačíky et al.
572 (2013) provided layer numbers for the dates of the 1980s arranged ascending from top to
573 bottom. However, the archives of the 1980s excavations and the Gliwice Radiocarbon
574 Laboratory include a radiocarbon date submission sheet, on which Bárta numbered the layers
575 descending from bottom to top.

576
577 As best we can establish, the earliest human occupation at TrB is found in layer B-2,
578 dated to 38.3–35.8 ky cal BP. This period is largely coeval with the GI-8 interstadial between
579 38.2 and 36.5 ky b2k (Rasmussen et al. 2014) which explains the soil formation found related
580 with layer B-2. This layer can be correlated with the lowest archaeological layer of Bárta found
581 in an Interpleniglacial soil in area A1. Besides the same stratigraphic position, the low number
582 of artefacts and the lack of Gravettian character also coincide with the features presented by
583 Bárta (1988) for the lowest layer. The thin list of tool types does not allow specifying the
584 cultural affiliation of this lithic industry. In Western Slovakia, Dzeravá skála Cave occupation
585 yielded Aurignacian osseous points dated to between 38.3 and 33.2 ky cal BP (OxA-15534 and
586 15535) (Davies and Hedges 2005); in Moravia modern human teeth at Mladeč Cave date to
587 between 36.2 and 34.3 ky cal BP (Wild et al. 2005); and at Stránská Skála Aurignacian dates
588 fall between 38.7 and 31.8 ky cal BP (Svoboda 2003). Based on the chronological overlap of
589 these sites we suspect that layer B-2 belongs to the Aurignacian occupation of the Western
590 Carpathians.

591 The next occupation is in layer A2-3. This layer yielded the densest archaeological
592 remains, as being the main Gravettian occupation by the definition of Bárta (1988). The lithic
593 toolkit contains all the armatures of the Late Gravettian of Central Europe (Lengyel 2016, 2018;
594 Lengyel and Wilczyński 2018). Vlačíky et al. (2013) described a toolkit from this layer of the
595 2008 excavation consisting of 13 backed bladelets, five retouched blades, one pointed retouched
596 blade, and two burins. One of the burins was made on a flake and the rest of the tools are blades.
597 The abundancy of the 2008 collection and the typological spectrum correlates with our results.
598 The calendric age 30.5 k - 29.0 ky cal BP falls also into the span of the Late Gravettian

599 chronology (Lengyel and Wilczyński 2018; Wilczyński et al. in press) and correlates with the
600 GS-5.1 stadial phase (Rasmussen et al. 2014). Besides the radiocarbon ages, the geological data
601 showed this layer was embedded within a windblown sediment, partially redeposited in slope
602 position, which is typical for stadial events. The sole artistic object is a pendant made of a deer
603 canine tooth. This raw material is absent in the Pavlovian of Southern Moravia, where personal
604 ornaments were most often made of fox and wolf incisors and canines (Láznicková-Galetová
605 2011; Wojtal et al., 2012; 2018), and rarely from reindeer teeth (Wojtal et al., 2012). A single
606 exemplar of a pendant made of red deer canine was found at Lubná II site of similar age, which
607 is decorated by incisions (Šída 2015, Fig. 154, 155).

608 Superposing layer A2-3, layer A2-2 also belong to the Late Gravettian occupation of
609 the area on the basis of the backed bladelets, the rectangle of Late Gravettian type, the fléchette
610 and the Vachons point (Lengyel 2015, 2016, 2018; Wilczyński 2016). The sole difference
611 between A2-3 and A2-2 is the lack of Gravette/microgravette points in A2-2. Vlačíky et al.
612 (2013) found only a few erratic flint blade tools in this layer in 2008: a burin, an endscraper-
613 burin combination, and a backed bladelet. The calibrated radiocarbon age 29.0 - 27.1 ky cal
614 BP falls into the chronological position of this type of lithic industry of Central Europe (Lengyel
615 and Wilczyński 2018; Wilczyński et al. in press), which is coeval mostly with GS-4 stadial
616 between 28.6 and 27.8 ky b2k and overlaps GI-4, GI-3 and GS-3 (Rasmussen et al. 2014).

617 On the basis of the radiocarbon measurements, the next human occupation is the BLP
618 assemblage of area B in layer B-1 dated to between 27.7 and 25.9 ky cal BP. The period between
619 27.7 and 25.9 ky cal BP corresponds with GS-3 stadial leading to the Last Glacial Maximum
620 (Rasmussen et al. 2014). The mollusc faunal spectra support the radiometric age correlation
621 and showed identity between layers B-1 and A2-1. The molluscan faunas of layers B-1 and A2-
622 1 include species with cold preference indicating the coldest period in the stratigraphic sequence
623 at TrB, which fairly corresponds with the development of the LGM in the region. Also, the gley
624 soil formation in layer B-1, which is the only periglacial phenomenon in the strata, further
625 supports the estimated early LGM chronological position of layer B-1. However, the results of
626 charcoal analysis are only partially supportive. The charcoal remains mainly derived from the
627 human gathering of firewood and it is likely that all available wood was chosen for fuel. In the
628 Weichselian glacial conditions of Central Europe *Pinus* and *Picea* or *Larix* are the most frequent
629 taxa of trees found in the charcoal assemblages from the archaeological sites before and during
630 LGM (Willis and van Andel 2004). The stratigraphic record at TrB shows a change in the
631 distribution of tree species in area A2 from the bottom to the top. The widest spectrum of trees
632 was found in layers A2-3 and B-1, in similar shares. Layer A2-2 yielded only *Picea* or *Larix*,
633 and layer A2-1 is the only one to include *Pinus sylvestris-mugo*. This distribution shows that
634 during occupations A2-3 and B-1 a possibly similar vegetal environment characterized the Váh
635 valley. There is a dominance of *Picea* or *Larix* charcoals in layers A2-2 and B-2, but it is also
636 probable that the unspecified coniferous charcoal fragments belong to *Pinus*. However, we
637 suspect that a change in charcoal assemblages from *Picea* or *Larix*-dominated layers in A2-3,
638 A2-2 and B-1 to the presence of *Pinus sylvestris-mugo* in A2-1 might be significant in the
639 vegetation at the beginning of the LGM. Based on recent ecological conditions, both trees *Picea*
640 or *Larix*, most likely *Picea abies* and *Larix decidua* in Central European sites, can be regarded
641 as growing on semi-permanently frozen soils, although *Larix decidua* is better adapted to colder
642 conditions and nowadays grows in the mountains together with *Pinus cembra* above *Picea*
643 *abies*-dominated forests. *Pinus cembra* and *Pinus sylvestris* together with *P. mugo* can also
644 grow under conditions of a full-glacial environment (Willis et al. 2000). The slight decrease in
645 coniferous wood charcoal abundance in layer A2-1 may also indicate a cooling climate. Out of
646 the 18 snail species identified, four have woodland preference and another four prefer
647 intermediate environment between open habitat and woodland. Except the 89.1% in layer A2-
648 3, the proportion of snails preferring open habitat makes up between 94.4 and 99.8% of all

649 species in each layer. Thus, compared to layers A2-2, B-1 and A2-1, during the formation of
650 layer A2-3 a slightly more expanded forest cover can be reconstructed, similarly to what has
651 been recovered from Pavlovian sites dated to 31 ky cal BP in nearby Moravia (Baresford-Jones
652 et al. 2010; Cichocki et al. 2014; Svoboda et al. 2015), while the coniferous trees may have
653 formed only patches of trees near the site at the onset of the LGM. These results indicate that
654 LGM environmental conditions might have been fully formed already during the formation of
655 Layer A2-1 in the Váh valley.

656 The archaeological, radiometric, paleobotanical, stratigraphic, and snail faunal
657 evidences straightforwardly generate an argument for the cultural classification of layer B-1 in
658 the UP in ECE. BLP-maker hunter-gatherers were primarily associated with the Middle to
659 Upper Palaeolithic transitional period, the EUP (Škrdla et al. 2014) and the Late Gravettian
660 (Simán 1990; Lengyel et al. 2016), but never occurred postdating the Late Gravettian. The
661 dating results argue against a MP-UP transitional Szeletian occupation at the TrB site; this phase
662 is dated to 37–44 ky cal BP in the region (Kaminská et al. 2011; Škrdla et al. 2014; Hauck et
663 al. 2016). The lack of Gravettian armatures in TrB Layer B-1 does not allow identifying this
664 assemblage as Late Gravettian with bifacial leaf points, because each Late Gravettian
665 assemblage with leaf points has at least three further types of the Gravettian armature besides
666 the bifacial tools and the retouched points (Novák 2008; Lengyel et al. 2016), which are missing
667 in the layer B-1 assemblage. The lack of diagnostic Gravettian tool types in the latest human
668 occupations at TrB actually corresponds with the gradual disappearance of Gravettian type
669 armature in the archaeological record of ECE during the transition from the Late Gravettian to
670 the Epigravettian as the LGM developed its apex (Lengyel 2016, 2018; Lengyel and Wilczyński
671 2018). Unfortunately, the pendants made of small pebbles in layer B-1 do not help decide where
672 this occupation may belong, because similar artefacts are found in both Late Gravettian and
673 Epigravettian contexts of ECE (Montet-White 1990, Fig IX-14; Kazior et al. 1998, Fig. 36).
674 The Layer B-1 lithic assemblage presents also a shift in raw material economy compared to
675 layers A2-3 and A2-2 with having been made mostly from the local radiolarite. This fits a
676 general tendency found in the archaeological record of the Carpathian Basin, in what the lithic
677 raw material procurement strategy changes from distant to local as the Late Gravettian fades
678 out and the Early Epigravettian emerges at the onset of the LGM (Svoboda and Novák 2004;
679 Kozłowski 2013; Lengyel 2014, 2018). Therefore, the chronological position of layer B-1 BLP
680 industry is unique in ECE. The only similar archaeological record is found in Western Europe
681 where the formation of the BLP producing Middle Solutrean was linked with the global cooling
682 by the LGM (Banks et al., 2009; Renard 2011). Up to date it is unsafe to interpret the TrB BLP
683 assemblage as Solutrean. Most likely we need to regard the BLP as a tool type that emerged in
684 the Late Middle Palaeolithic in Neanderthal technology (Richter 2016) but kept recurring with
685 uneven frequency throughout the Bohunician (Škrdla 2017), Jankovichian (Mester 2017),
686 Szeletian (Mester 2018), Aurignacian (Oliva 1990), and Gravettian (Lengyel et al. 2016) up to
687 the LGM, and it is not a distinctive '*fossile directeur*'.

688 In the sequence of human occupations at TrB, it is only layer A2-1 that fully represents
689 Early Epigravettian features of ECE (Lengyel 2018) by lacking any piece of distant lithic raw
690 material and Gravettian armature. The dating of layer A2-1 places the occurrence of the Early
691 Epigravettian type lithic industry to ca. 26.0 ky cal BP, which is 2.0 millennia earlier than
692 expected. The archaeological results of the research at TrB suggest that among the possible
693 timing of the LGM extension (Hughes and Gibbard 2015; Hughes et al. 2016; Stroeven et al.
694 2016; Patton et al. 2017) probably the most secure is to follow the chronology of Clark et al.
695 (2009), which showed the terrestrial ice sheets reached their maximum extent by 26.5 ky cal
696 BP at the earliest on global scale based on the Greenland ice core GS-3 stadial record (Hughes
697 and Gibbard 2015). Therefore, dating any archaeological record linked with the advance of the
698 LGM might produce earlier determinations than expected.

699 **6. Disclosure Statement**

700

701 No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

702

703 **7. References**

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- Figure 8. Formal tools of layer A2-3 (1-15) and layer B-1 (16-21). 1–3: end-scraper; 4–5: burin; 6: retouched blade; 7: splintered tool; 8–10: microgravette; 11: Vachons point; 12–13: backed and ventrally truncated bladelets (Late Gravettian rectangle) 14: fléchette; 15: retouched point; 16, 17, 19, 20: bifacial leaf point; 19: bifacial knife. 1, 5–9, 12, 14: erratic flint; 2, 4, 6: Jurassic flint; 3, 10: obsidian Carpathian 2 type; 11, 15–20: radiolarite; 13: chert.
- Figure 9. Use wear traces on bifacial tools.
- Figure 10. Pierced pebble pendants of layer B-1 (1), two of which have incision on their edges (2), and the tooth pendant of layer A2-3 (3).
- Figure 11. The distribution of mollusc fauna in the archaeological layers.

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Tables

Table 1. Radiocarbon dates of the site

Lab code	layer	date	std	trench	cal BP 95.4%	sample	origin	reference
GrA-42311	A2-1	22330	110	2008/B1	27025-26230	charcoal	arch. layer	Vlačíky et al. 2013
Poz-97252	A2-1	22470	150	2017/A2	27110-26220	charcoal	hearth	this paper
Gd-4011	A2-2	20300	500	27/85	25695-23367	charcoal	hearth	Bárta 1988
GrA-16126	A2-2	23100	150	27/85	27662-27126	charcoal	arch. layer	Verpoorte 2001
GrA-44244	A2-2	23210	100	2008/B3	27684-27283	charcoal	arch. layer	Vlačíky et al. 2013
Gd-4014	A2-2	23400	700	29/85	29036-26191	charcoal	hearth	Bárta 1988
Gd-2490	A2-2	23700	500	28/85	28894-27055	charcoal	arch. layer	Bárta 1988
Poz-101182	A2-2	23650	230	2017/A2	28447-27574	bone	arch. layer	this paper
Poz-101178	A2-2	25430	270	2017/A2	29886-28593	bone	arch. layer	this paper
Gd-4010	A2-3	23100	1200	23/83-84	30395-25280	charcoal	hearth	Bárta 1988
GrA-42312	A2-3	24540	130	2008/A3	28871-28261	charcoal	arch. layer	Vlačíky et al. 2013
GrA-16163	A2-3	25130	170	20/83	29584-28764	charcoal	arch. layer	Verpoorte 2001
Poz-101180	A2-3	25760	290	2017/A2	30544-29007	bone	arch. layer	this paper
GrA-16162	A2-3	25650	160	24/1983-84	30365-29365	charcoal	arch. layer	Verpoorte 2001
Poz-101181	A2-3	25310	300	2017/A2	30810-29435	bone	arch. layer	this paper
Poz-97362	B-1	22480	220	2017/B2	27042-25984	charcoal	arch. layer	this paper
Gd-4009	B-1	22500	600	B/83	27836-25720	charcoal	arch. layer	Bárta 1988
Gd-4016	B-1	22800	600	1B/1982	28136-25917	charcoal	arch. layer	Bárta 1988
GrA-16161	B-1	23280	140	2B/1983	27753-27296	charcoal	arch. layer	Verpoorte 2001
Poz-97254	B-1	24260	180	2017/B2	28994-28158	charcoal	arch. layer	this paper
Poz-97253	B-1	24400	180	2017/B2	29046-28203	charcoal	arch. layer	this paper
GrA-16139	?	29910	260	1B/18	34510-33605	charcoal	?	Verpoorte 2001
Poz-101822	B-2	32190	460	2017/B1	38315-35887	charcoal	arch. layer	this paper

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Table 2. Litho- and pedological characteristic of trenches A2, B1 and B2.

Depth (m)	Description	Interpretation (soils/archaeological layers)
Trench A2 section (north wall)		
0.0–0.17	clayey loam, grey-yellow, HCl ++, sharp limit in color	soil horizon Ap

0.17–0.80	calcareous loess with numerous pseudomycelium and molluscs, HCl+++ , clear boundary	soil horizon Ck	
0.80–0.95	calcareous loam, light pale yellow, numerous bones and charcoals, HCl +, sharp undulated boundary,	cultural layer (A2-3)	
0.95–1.40	calcareous loam, olive yellow, HCl+, diffuse boundary	poorly developed soil (interstadial rank)	
1.40–2.45 (drilling)	massive calcareous loam, yellow-grey, fine iron hydroxide bands, HCl++	aeolian-solifluction loess layer	
Trench B1 section (north wall)			
0.0–0.30	clayey loam, brown-grey, overgrown with roots of modern plants, HCl-, clear boundary	soil horizon Ap	recent soil
0.30–0.57	silt loam, grey, numerous roots, tubules with coprolites, HCl-, clear border	soil horizon Et	
0.57–1.10	clayey loam, numerous roots and coprolites, compacted, with cracks from drying, HCl-, boundary visible in color	soil horizon Bt	
1.10–1.60	clayey loam, mosaic of brown and dark grey colors - marble with bioglyphs, clay coatings - clear traces of illuviation, lower boundary visible in clour and presence of carbonates	soil horizon BC	
1.60–2.10	non calcareous clayey loam, grey-yellow, numerous pseudomycelia (vertical) and nodule (2-3 mm), numerous concretions of Fe and MN-Fe (1-2 mm in diameter), numerous biochannels with coprolites, HCl+, sharp border in colour	soil horizon C	
2.10–2.70	silt loam, grey-dark yellow, pseudomycelia and nodule as above, in the lower part numerous and large molluscs filled with soil-repellent material (average 15-20 cm), although no artifacts were found here, this layer corresponds with the upper cultural layer of area B found in trench B2, HCl+, clear boundary	soil horizon Ab	buried soil
2.70–2.90	silt loam, grey-brown, HCl +, diffuse boundary	soil horizon Btb	
2.90–6.25	calcareous loam, brown-grey, numerous channels with coprolites the top includes the lower cultural layer (B-2) of area B	aeolian-solifluction loess layer	
Trench B2 section (west wall)			
0.0–0.30	clayey loam, brown-grey, HCl+, clear boundary	soil horizon Ap	heap
0.30–0.35	calcareous loam HCl+++ , clear boundary	soil horizon Ck	
0.35–1.15	clayey loam, brownish-red, intersected with vertical slits, overgrown, numerous channels, visible illuvial clay coatings, HCl-	soil horizon Bt	recent soil
1.15–1.55	clayey loam, light brownish-red, numerous bioglyphs, HCl-, boundary visible in carbonates	soil horizon BC	
1.55–2.15	calcareous clayey loam, at a depth of 1.90-1.95 m, there is a manganese layer detected also in TB4 at a depth of 1.80-1.82 m, HCl +, clear boundary	soil horizon C, loess	
2.15–2.70	numerous artifacts, animal bones, charcoals, bioturbations, HCl+	upper cultural layer	

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Table 3. Trenčianske Bohuslavice lithic tool kit raw material composition.

	A2-1	A2-2	A2-3	B-1	B-2	Total
radiolarite	8	43	303	77	1	432
	100,0%	35,2%	35,7%	88,5%	100,0%	40,5%
erratic flint	0	67	462	9	0	538
	0,0%	54,9%	54,5%	10,3%	0,0%	50,5%

jurassic flint	0	2	47	0	0	49
	0,0%	1,6%	5,5%	0,0%	0,0%	4,6%
obsidian	0	4	22	0	0	26
	0,0%	3,3%	2,6%	0,0%	0,0%	2,4%
chert	0	6	14	1	0	21
	0,0%	4,9%	1,7%	1,1%	0,0%	2,0%
Total	8	122	848	87	1	1066
	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

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Table 4. Trenčianske Bohuslavice retouched tools inventories of areas A2, B1 and B2.

	A2-1	A2-2	A2-3	B-1	B-2	Total
Domestic tools						
endscraper	2	12	85	7	0	106
	25.0%	9.8%	10.0%	8.0%	0.0%	9.9%
burin	2	32	214	7	0	255
	25.0%	26.2%	25.2%	8.0%	0.0%	23.9%
edge-retouched	3	41	304	44	1	393
	37.5%	33.6%	35.8%	50.6%	100.0%	36.9%
splintered	1	3	33	1	0	38
	12.5%	2.5%	3.9%	1.1%	0.0%	3.6%
borer	0	1	7	0	0	8
	0.0%	0.8%	0.8%	0.0%	0.0%	0.8%
truncated	0	3	18	5	0	26
	0.0%	2.5%	2.1%	5.7%	0.0%	2.4%
combined	0	2	13	0	0	15
	0.0%	1.6%	1.5%	0.0%	0.0%	1.4%
knife	0	0	0	1	0	1
	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.1%	0.0%	0.1%
Armature						
backed	0	14	50	0	0	64
	0.0%	11.5%	5.9%	0.0%	0.0%	6.0%
backed-truncated	0	0	1	0	0	1
	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%
rectangle	0	0	3	0	0	3
	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%
LG rectangle	0	5	67	1	0	73
	0.0%	4.1%	7.9%	1.1%	0.0%	6.8%
Gravette/microgravette	0	0	16	0	0	16
	0.0%	0.0%	1.9%	0.0%	0.0%	1.5%
retouched point	0	8	30	3	0	41
	0.0%	6.6%	3.5%	3.4%	0.0%	3.8%

fléchette	0	1	3	0	0	4
	0.0%	0.8%	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%
Vachons point	0	0	3	0	0	3
	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%
bifacial leaf point	0	0	1	18	0	19
	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	20.7%	0.0%	1.8%
Total	8	122	848	87	1	1066
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

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figure 11

